

Training materials on organic plant breeding

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LiveSeeding - Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe is a 4-year Innovation Action funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project started in October 2022 and brings together 37 organisations operating in 16 European countries. LiveSeeding provides science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help achieve 100 % organic seed.

LiveSeeding contributes to the transition towards environmentally-friendly, climate-neutral, healthy and fair food systems through a **PUSH-PULL-ENABLE strategy** to

- enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PUSH),
- increase and stabilise the market demand for organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PULL),
- foster an enabling policy and regulatory environment where both demand and supply can harmoniously and productively negotiate without irrelevant constraints due to legal restrictions and/or regulatory fragmentation (ENABLE).

LiveSeeding addresses the topics in a **holistic multi-actor, multi-stakeholder, participatory approach** involving stakeholders along the value chain in 17 local **Living Labs (LLs)** and 3 established networks of organic breeders (**ECO-PB**), seed savers (**ECLLD**) and Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (**MUFPP**). 15 European countries cover the different pedoclimatic zones and socio-economic contexts, including countries with a low level of development in organic seed and breeding in East and South Europe.

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Summary

Current agricultural production systems face great challenges. Climate change and its far-reaching impacts—such as erratic rainfall patterns and rising global temperatures – combined with unsustainable farming practice - based on intensive monocrop, high-input agriculture, that disrupts soil health, accelerates erosion of agrobiodiversity—compromise the future of our food security and sovereignty in Europe.

Organic agriculture, when combined with the deliberate enhancement of cultivated biodiversity, offers a powerful means of mitigating and even reversing these threats. This approach contributes to the development of globally sustainable food systems that are less polluting and more genetically diverse, and therefore inherently more resilient and adaptable in confronting these complex challenges.

A key pillar in achieving this transformation lies in the improvement of seeds and crop varieties through targeted plant breeding. Seeds are fundamental to agricultural production, and their enhancement—especially under organic conditions—provides vast potential for fostering sustainability. Organic plant breeding, which includes the recovery and improvement of traditional landraces as well as the creation of new genetic variations, is essential for cultivating robust and diverse plant populations suited to organic systems.

*The LiveSeeding project, aims to enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming. **Training in organic seed and plant breeding** key concepts, terms, strategies and tools available **represents a key approach to change farming practices.***

*Deliverable 1.1 is an exhaustive compilation of **training materials in organic breeding**. Training materials are divided into five thematic modules, structured in 3-4 units each, covering from the basic aspects of organic breeding to the most sophisticated available tools, all respectful of the principles of organic production.*

Each training module has a training outline that clearly identifies the scope of the training, the learning objectives and target audience, the learning modalities, methodology and materials, as well as the learning assessment method. The training outline has been developed as a common approach for all training materials and training-related deliverables in the project. The supporting materials include i) PowerPoint presentations prepared by the lecturers; ii) the recordings of the sessions; iii) other support learning materials such as videos, exercises, case studies etc. & iv) the training outline for each Module.

1. Justification and main objectives

Current agricultural production systems face great challenges. Climate change and its pedoclimatic consequences (e.g. drought, scarcity and worse quality of water for irrigation, erratic rains, increase in temperatures), the negative impacts of intensive monoculture production systems, the genetic erosion of cultivated biodiversity exacerbated in recent decades, pollution and alteration of soil balances, among other aspects, seriously compromise the sovereignty and food security of the future.

In this context, organic production, together with the promotion of greater cultivated biodiversity, can contribute to significantly mitigate these risks and even reverse them, contributing positively towards more sustainable productive systems, less demanding on inputs and less polluting, more genetically diverse and consequently more adaptable, resilient and dynamic.

Seeds are the foundation of life and the cornerstone of food production.

To advance organic farming, we must take a synergistic approach based on two key pillars for enhancing agrobiodiversity:

- by preserving, improving, and valuing genetic resources;
- by genetic improvement of plant populations and development of new cultivars within organic production systems—a process known as organic breeding.

Whenever possible, it is essential to encourage the active and informed participation of all stakeholders in the value chain—farmers, breeders, technicians, retailers, consumers, end users, and public authorities. Their collective knowledge can support effective decision-making in organic breeding through participatory plant breeding, while also helping to build or strengthen the socioeconomic networks that support sustainable agriculture.

The aim of Task 1.4 of LiveSeeding project is to **contribute to training** in the main concepts, terms, strategies and tools available **in organic breeding**, with a considerable amount of training materials aimed at a wide range of actors.

These materials have initially been generated as online courses, taught in five sessions between the months of January and March 2025, and include i) the PowerPoint presentations prepared by the lecturers (covering concepts, practical examples, demonstrations, tutorials, additional materials suggested to work on in the sessions themselves, questionnaires and homework), ii) the recordings of these sessions; iii) other support learning materials & iv) the training outline for each Module that can be used by trainers that want to deliver lectures based on LiveSeeding materials.

Our training materials are divided into five thematic modules, one for each session. Each module consists of three or four units that cover all aspects, from the basics of organic breeding to the most sophisticated available tools, while respecting the principles of organic production and organic breeding (i.e. target molecular breeding

tools for diagnostics use only, not to substitute the direct selection in the target environment).

These materials offer a comprehensive perspective on organic breeding knowledge, concepts, strategies, tools and opportunities, adapted to a diverse group of target trainees, from organic farmers to PhD students of different levels (high school, undergraduates and/or MSc students) and scientists, seed producers, organic breeders, and any others involved in the value chain of organic systems with interest in some (or all) the main issues in organic breeding.

Some units are suitable for most of the mentioned trainee profiles (particularly those in Modules 1 and 2), while other materials are aimed at more technical and advanced audience (from Module 3 onward), such as MSc and PhD students, breeders or scientists. More details on the specific units and training objectives are provided in the next section.

2. Description of the training modules

The training courses were organized into five thematic modules. Each training module is divided into three or four units. The units were implemented as online webinars and included a presentation, as well as dynamic interactions with trainees, in the form of quizzes, general discussions, and tutor-led work and hands-on exercises during sessions and/or homework assignments. *These modules and corresponding links in Organic Eprint and ECO PB are:*

Module 1: *Plant Genetic Resources (PGRs): collection, conservation and exchange to support the increase of agrobiodiversity in farming systems (3 units).*

Organic Eprint link: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/54728/>

ECO PB: <https://www.eco-pb.org/trainings.html>

Module 2: *Phenomics: approaches and tools for genetic resources and breeding material characterization (4 units).*

Organic Eprint link: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/54984/>

ECO PB: <https://www.eco-pb.org/trainings.html>

Module 3: *Breeding methods fundamentals (4 units)*

Organic Eprint link: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/54985/>

ECO PB: <https://www.eco-pb.org/trainings.html>

Module 4: *Development and application of molecular methods in organic breeding (4 units)*

ECO PB: <https://www.eco-pb.org/trainings.html>

Organic Eprint link: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/55664/>

Module 5: *Organic heterogeneous material (OHM) design and development (4 units).*

Organic Eprint link: <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/55665/>

ECO PB: <https://www.eco-pb.org/trainings.html>

All training modules have a **common training outline** that clearly identifies the scope of the training, the learning objectives and target audience, the learning modalities, methodology and materials, as well as the learning assessment method.

The training outline and the modular approach have been developed as a common approach for all training materials and training-related deliverables in the project (each work package as a training task) in order to create better learning paths that can support knowledge transfer and can also ensure easy replicability of trainings. The modular approach also allows to create new trainings in the future that make use of individual modules or units from various work packages in order to create new trainings targeted to specific groups and learning needs.

The framing of common training outline and the learning methodology has been curated by **Stephanie Mothes (ITAB, FR)** with the support of **Mariano Iossa (FiBL Europe)** and **Francesca Gori (RSR)** within the work of the Training Task Force (T7.2)

2.1 Module 1 - Plant Genetic Resources (PGRs): collection, conservation and exchange to support the increase of agrobiodiversity in farming systems

Topics: Plant genetic resources (PGRs) are essential for breeding. The agrobiodiversity encompassed in modern varieties, landraces and ecotypes as well as wild relatives must be preserved i) to mitigate genetic erosion and, therefore, ii) to ensure that these resources are available to face future challenges (e.g. climate change, new pathogens, new preferences) and iii) contribute to a diverse and resilient agrifood sector. Seedbanks as *ex situ* conservation structures, community seedbanks (CSBs), breeding and pre-breeding collections, are among the most usual *ex situ* conservation methods. Community seed banks and farmers' collections are examples of *in situ* conservation.

Target groups: In this module, the targeted actors learn about methodologies and strategies related to the conservation, use and exchange of genetics resources.

This module is open to (although not limited to) farmers (and more specifically to the ones committed with agroecology, preservation of landraces and involved in selection and plant breeding) and students (from the high school level to MSc level, especially students in plant breeding, plant production or agronomy).

Learning objectives: At the end of the training, the trainee received input and contacts to support:

- Management of own genetic resources;

- Understanding about PGR conservation methodologies;
- Development of own PGR collection initiatives

Number of units: 3

2.1.1 Unit 1 - Public/Institutional seedbanks: PGRs collection, conservation and exchange

Lecturer(s): Prof. Adrián Rodríguez-Burruezo and MSc Eva M. Solbes

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) – COMAV Institute

Topics: main procedures and knowledge in the collection, *ex situ* conservation, multiplication and exchange of PGRs in the frame of Institutional seedbanks.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.1.2 Unit 2 - Pre-breeding: from genetic resources characterisation to their use in breeding programmes

Lecturer(s): Dr. Vladimir Meglic

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Agricultural Institute of Slovenia (KIS)

Topics: Breeders collections, pre-breeding materials, primarily use of PGRs in breeding programmes.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.1.3 Unit 3 - Community seed banks: collection, dynamic management and exchange

Lecturer(s): Dr. Kostas Koutis and Riccardo Bocci

Supporting contributor: Gabriele Maneo (EC-LLD)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Aegilops (AEG), Rete Semi Rurali (RSR), Let's Liberate Diversity (EC-LLD)

Topics: Farmers collections, local seed networks, on farm conservation, seed exchange in the frame of farmers' association or Community seedbanks, participatory seed conservation and multiplication, etc.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.2 Module 2 - Phenomics: approaches and tools for genetic

resources and breeding material characterization

Topics: PGRs phenotyping and characterization is essential: i) to estimate and manage their diversity and ii) to identify sources of variation in traits of interest for breeding. To accomplish these purposes a wide range of descriptors, tools and strategies are available. These allow to characterize properly and comprehensively the agrobiodiversity available in standardized parameters, follow the flow of seeds lots, manage the information in an efficient way and share phenomic and agronomic info to other interested actors. One unit (unit 5), planned at first and entitled "Methods for phenotyping and selection of added-value traits" (e.g. taste and nutritional value), was not finally given because of the lack of availability of lecturers (ITAB). The unit primarily focused on phenotyping plant populations for nutritional value and organoleptic quality, including taste and flavour, in both raw and processed foods. The goal was to present how to include these traits in the breeding process to favour the valorization of the selected materials using a "differentiated quality" approach. Nevertheless, as a contingency plan, many of these concepts were incorporated into some of the final units of the module.

Target groups: In this module, the targeted actors learn about the main methodologies for phenotyping PGRs, keep traceability of seeds lots, and tools to manage the phenomic info.

This module is open to seed networks managers, a wide range of organic farmers (particular interest for farmers committed with agroecology, preservation of landraces and starting in breeding their own varieties), organic breeders and students (mainly undergraduate University degrees and MSc students in plant breeding).

Learning objectives: At the end of the training, the trainee should be able to:

- Know (and know "how-to-use") the main descriptors and traits used in germplasm characterization
- Manage, in a practical way, crop descriptors and tools aimed to trace and keep the track of seeds lots
- Know the most relevant agronomic traits and added-value traits and know how to characterise varieties with them

Number of units: 4

2.2.1 Unit 1 - Main descriptors used worldwide in characterizing plant genetic resources

Lecturer(s): Prof. Adrián Rodríguez-Burruezo

LIVSEEDING partner(s): Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) – COMAV Institute

Topics: Common descriptors and setlists of traits used by breeders, researchers and seed multipliers to characterise exhaustively PGRs. IPGRI/BIOVERSITY descriptors, High throughout phenomic tools, based on image treatment, like Tomato Analyser™.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.2.2 Unit 2 - Intro to SHiNeMaS : a web tool dedicated to Seed Lots History, Phenotyping & Cultural Practices

Lecturer(s): MSc Yannick de Oliveira and Dr. Isabelle Goldringer

LIVESEEDING partner(s): INRAe

Topics: management of data aimed at the traceability of seed lots history, available info and growing conditions, based on the example of SHiNeMaS , a web tool designed for these specific purposes.

2.2.3 Unit 3 - Guidelines and examples of good practices in data management

Lecturer(s): MSc Yannick de Oliveira and Dr. Isabelle Goldringer

LIVESEEDING partner(s): INRAe

Topics: data management plans and legal constraint, guidelines to manage data (standard data and metadata), main terms and vocabulary, licenses, data warehouses.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.2.4 Unit 4 - Methods for phenotyping & selection of agronomic traits of interest in organic farming

Lecturer(s): Prof. Pedro Mendes Moreira

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra (IPC)

Topics: mean methodologies to phenotype plant populations based on agronomic traits, selection of individuals for these traits, in the frame of organic farming. Illustrative examples of crops and projects on these issues.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.3 Module 3 - Breeding methods fundamentals

Topics: Plant breeding encompass a range of strategies to achieve the improvement of plant varieties and populations. From the initial stage of suitable genetic variation (essential for breeder's success) to the different methodologies used in building new

improved varieties. A wide perspective on breeding methods is essential for an efficient breeding work and a satisfactory response to selection. The availability of sources of variation to provide response to breeding objectives is the first step. To achieve that, breeders can perform preliminary screenings or generate new variation through different methods. Then, choosing and developing suitable breeding methodologies is also a key issue, as it must adapt the kind of traits we want to improve, the reproductive system of the species managed and/or the kind of variety or population we have as target. Moreover, many parameters which support and help breeders' decision taking must be considered (e.g. correlations, heritability, combining ability). Finally, and particularly in the frame of organic breeding, a participatory approach has gained attention in the last years. Participatory breeding enables a more efficient selection of lines by considering the opinion of the most relevant socioeconomic actors of the value chain (e.g. breeders, scientists, farmers, citizenship, retailers).

Target groups: In this module, the targeted trainees will learn about the most relevant particularities, methodologies and strategies related and aimed at organic breeding. This module is open to seed networks managers, a wide range of organic farmers (particular interest for farmers committed with agroecology, preservation of landraces and starting in breeding their own varieties), organic breeders and students (mainly University undergraduates, MSc or even PhD students in plant breeding).

Learning objectives: At the end of the training, the trainee should be able to:

- Know how to create genetic variation to start the breeding process
- Know the most relevant parameters to support breeders' work and selections
- Get a better understanding about breeding strategies in the context of organic systems, including participatory approaches

Number of units: 4

2.3.1 Unit 1 – Generation of new diversity

Lecturer(s): MSc Neus Ortega-Albero and Prof. Adrián Rodríguez-Burruezo

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) – COMAV Institute

Topics: the need of variation for breeders and for a more healthy and resilient farming system, variation available on plant varieties (intra and intervarietal), introduction of new variation, creation of new variation by hybridization, further development of lines (e.g. controlled selfings or backcrossings, mixtures, organic heterogeneous materials), experimental populations (e.g. NILS/near isogenic lines, MAGIC/Multiparent Advanced Generation InterCross).

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.3.2 Unit 2 - Common methods and strategies in organic breeding

Lecturer(s): Prof. Pedro Mendes Moreira (IPC), Prof. Adrian Rodríguez-Burruezo (UPV) and Dr. Barbara Pipan (KIS)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): IPC and KIS

Topics: fundamentals on methods and strategies, methods based on already existing diverse populations or based on previous hybridization, mass selection, individual selection, pedigree method, backcross method, composite cross populations (CCPs) selection. Practical examples with initiatives aimed at allogamous crops (maize, IPC) and autogamous crops (common bean, KIS)

Unit duration: 2:00 h

2.3.3 Unit 3 - Calculation and evaluation of key breeding parameters

Lecturer(s): Prof. Adrian Rodríguez-Burruezo (UPV) and Dr. Barbara Pipan (KIS)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): UPV and KIS

Topics: estimation and application of the main breeding parameters. Qualitative traits. Quantitative traits. Studies of traits inheritance. Chi square tests. Correlations, heritability, coefficients of variation, genotype-by-environment interaction. Practical examples based on research projects from KIS on common bean.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.3.4 Unit 4 - Fundamentals in participatory plant breeding

Lecturer(s): Prof. Pedro Mendes Moreira (IPC) and Dr. Véronique Chable (INRAe)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): IPC and INRAe

Topics: main issues considered on participatory plant breeding (PPB). Actors involved on PPB, rational contribution of the different actors to the breeding process and decision making, practical examples based on projects from IPC and INRAe.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.4 Module 4 - Development and application of molecular methods in organic breeding

Topics: Molecular methodologies are essential to support breeding to identify genes in experimental populations or in direct application in breeding activities. The

efficiency of phenotypic and agronomic evaluation and selection on the field can be increased thanks to previous knowledge about the info present in the DNA, in the shape of molecular markers and DNA polymorphisms. Molecular markers may help to perform DNA-polymorphisms-based screening of genotypes at the seedling stage for some traits and/or certain genetic backgrounds linked to specific DNA profiles, known as marker-assisted selection (MAS) and genomic selection. To achieve and tune such direct applications on breeding, other techniques and experimental populations must be developed and studied previously. Thus, Genome Wide Association compares the performance of large populations which segregate for traits of interest vs their genetic profile (based on DNA polymorphisms), with the aim of identifying specific DNA polymorphisms highly linked to the trait(s) of interest. Experimental populations build from parent lines which differ for those traits of interest are then essential for these assessments. The present module is aimed at training on the fundamentals of all these concepts.

Target groups: In this module, the targeted trainees will learn about the main issues related to MAS and genomic selection, as well as how these molecular approaches fit organic breeding principles and can be applied in organic breeding initiatives. From their implementation and application on breeding to the studies and experimental populations used in their development. This module is mainly aimed at organic breeders, researchers and students (at least University undergraduates on Agronomy, Biology, Biotechnology, MSc or even PhD students in plant breeding and biotechnology).

Learning objectives: At the end of the training, the trainee should be able to:

- Learn how to develop experimental populations useful in MAS&genomic selection
- Understand the fundamentals on how to link genetic profiles to traits of interest
- Learn the advantages of molecular markers and DNA profiles and examples of their application in breeding

Number of units: 4

2.4.1 Unit 1 – Genome Wide Association (GWA) and its potential for understanding the genetic basis of complex traits

Lecturer(s): MSc Neus Ortega-Albero

LIVESEEDING partner(s): Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) – COMAV Institute

Topics: basis of Genome Wide Association studies, practical examples, and practical exercise with the trainees during the session (based on Tassel5). Suggested homework based on this practical example.

Unit duration: 2:00 h

2.4.2 Unit 2 - Genomic Selection and its potential in organic breeding

Lecturer(s): Dr. Michael Schneider (FiBL)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): FiBL

Topics: The basis of genomic selection and its applications in organic breeding. The course will explain the simplest aspects of genome selection procedures and provide practical examples, online tutorials, and presentations. There will also be practical exercises with trainees.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.4.3 Unit 3 - Application of molecular marker-based selection in practical breeding

Lecturer(s): Dr. Barbara Pipan (KIS) and Dr. Mariateresa Lazzaro (FiBL)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): KIS and FiBL

Topics: how molecular-based selection can be applied and be useful in organic breeding, practical examples from projects managed by KIS and FiBL (lupins, common bean).

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.4.4 Unit 4 - Overview on experimental populations (e.g. NILs, RILs, introgression families, MAGIC) and their role in molecular breeding approaches

Lecturer(s): MSc Neus Ortega-Albero (UPV) and Dr. Vladimir Meglic (KIS)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): UPV and KIS

Topics: review of the most common experimental populations used in plant breeding and genetics (NILs, RILs, MPPs, MAGIC), several practical examples for Solanaceae crops (tomato, eggplants, peppers) from UPV activities, and wheat from KIS activities (Ecobreed project), cucumber, introgression/genome transfer of *Solanum lycopersicoides* into *S. lycopersicon*, QTL mapping based on these populations, etc.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.5 Module 5 - Organic heterogeneous material (OHM) design and

development

Topics: Organic Heterogeneous Material is a cultivar type that contributes to a more diverse, dynamically adaptable and resilient farming system. These populations, while showing uniformity for many morphological traits (e.g. fruit size and appearance, plant development), also preserve a heterogeneous genetic background for other traits which could be useful for adaptation to a wide range of pedoclimatic conditions. Thus, they are of particular interest in the context of organic farming and low input farming, as well as to face the climate change.

This module includes examples of OHMs already obtained, procedures to start the initial populations (composite cross populations or dynamic mixtures), breeding strategies and tools for genomic tracking of their evolution, as well as fundamentals on population genetics to understand their evolution. The present module is aimed at training on the fundamentals of all these concepts.

Target groups: In this module, the targeted trainees will learn about the main issues related to Organic Heterogeneous Materials (OHMs) concepts, fundamentals and development. From basic knowledge and population genetics dynamics to their development and tracking. This module is mainly aimed at organic breeders, researchers and students (at least University undergraduates on Agronomy, Biology, Biotechnology, MSc or even PhD students in plant breeding and biotechnology).

Learning objectives: At the end of the training, the trainee:

- knows the main methods to develop OHMs;
- understands how they evolve during their selection and development;
- has an overview of the main applications and opportunities of OHMs in organic farming.

Number of units: 4

2.5.1 Unit 1 – Composite Cross Populations: setting-up & selection

Lecturer(s): Prof. Adrian Rodríguez-Burruezo (UPV) and Dr. Isabelle Goldringer (INRAe)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): UPV and INRAe

Topics: what is a CCP, uses in genetics and organic breeding, contribution for a more diverse and resilient farming system, creation of CCPs, development towards OHMs, examples in vegetables and crop species, tutorized work based on research papers.

Unit duration: 2:00 h

2.5.2 Unit 2 - Dynamic mixtures: setting-up & selection

Lecturer(s): Prof. Pedro Mendes Moreira (IPC)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): IPC

Topics: explain mixtures in the context of breeding, uses in genetics and organic breeding, contribution for a more diverse and resilient farming system, creation of mixtures and further dynamic development, examples in vegetables and crop species.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.5.3 Unit 3 - Fundamentals of populations genetics applied to OHM development and use

Lecturer(s): Prof. Adrian Rodríguez-Burruezo (UPV) and Dr. Isabelle Goldringer (INRAe)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): UPV and INRAe

Topics: basis to understand population genetics, gene and genotype frequencies estimation, micro-evolutionary forces, practical example with online available simulator (PopGen).

Unit duration: 1:30 h

2.5.4 Unit 4 - Using genomics to track the evolution of heterogeneous organic materials

Lecturer(s): Dr. Michael Schneider (FiBL)

LIVESEEDING partner(s): FiBL

Topics: in connection with unit 3, in-depth review on genomic tracking of OHMs evolution, main parameters, practical examples from FiBL projects, etc.

Unit duration: 1:30 h

3. Materials

The available materials for each Module include:

- The Training Outline summarizing concepts and learning objectives for each training module;
- The corresponding presentations for each unit;
- The additional materials suggested in the presentations intended to widen the learning process(i) papers, ii) online available tutorials, iii) links to online available software and simulators, iv) links to projects, etc.);
- The live recordings of the courses, with the lecturers explaining in a dynamic way the different units, answering questions, solving the quizzes in common discussion, proposing activities and homework.

Table 1. List of training materials available in Organic EPrints repository.

	Links to Organic EPrints
Module 1	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/54728/
Module 2	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/54984/
Module 3	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/54985/
Module 4	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/55664/
Module 5	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/55665/

4. Attendees number and profiles

A considerable number of people attended the webinars of the different modules, reflecting a wide geographic distribution and diverse profiles. Overall, around 140 unique individuals from 28 different countries attended at least one of the five modules offered (Table 2).

Table 2. Representation of participants by country

Country	Number of attendees
Spain	14
France	13
Greece	12
Italy	12
Portugal	9
Germany	8
Poland	7
Hungary	7
Lithuania	6
Switzerland	6
Other ¹	48

As expected, some modules and units were open to more diverse profiles, like Modules 1 and 2, which were more basic and easily understandable for farmers, seed savers, breeders, students, and even MSc and PhD students. As a consequence, the number of people attending was much higher for those Modules (Table 3). Specifically, Module 1 engaged predominantly students (30%), breeders (28%), and researchers (24%). Module 2 attracted up to 70 participants, mostly researchers and students (Figure 1 and 2).

¹ Other countries include: Belgium, Ireland, United Kingdom, Netherlands, Norway, Serbia, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Latvia, Burkina Faso, Croatia, Tunisia, Nigeria, Nepal, Cabo Verde, Czech Republic, Slovenia, Austria.

Figure 1 Distribution of participants by actor groups - Module 1
 Figure 2 Distribution of participants by actor groups - Module 2

In contrast, Modules 3, 4 and 5 presented content that was more technical and closer to the frontiers of knowledge and, therefore, appealing to more specialized profiles (academics, MSc and PhD students, breeders and molecular breeders). Module 4, for example, engaged predominantly researchers and breeders. Similarly, Module 5 maintained the same profile of attendees (Figures 3 and 4).

Figure 4 Distribution of participants by actor groups - Module 4
 Figure 3 Distribution of participants by actor groups - Module 5

It is noticeable that a significant number of participants selected the "Other" category when indicating their actor profile. Entries grouped under "Other" included terms such as "seed activist," "landscape/seed manager," "NGO leader," "field agent," etc. This trend was particularly pronounced in Modules 2 and 3, where the share of "Other"

profiles came close to 30%, reflecting both the diversity of the audience and the limitations of the registration form.

Table 3. Number of attendees on the webinars for each Module and Unit.

	Date	Unit 1	Unit 2	Unit 3	Unit 4
Module 1	Jan 27th	105	102	96	---
Module 2	Feb 3rd	70	70	65	60
Module 3	Feb 13th	60	55	58	55
Module 4	March 4th	59	57	46	36
Module 5	March 7th	44	38	35	35